

**Studies in the Ligno-cellulose Group. Part. I. An
Investigation into the Constituents of Water
Hyacinth (*Eichornia Crassipes*).***

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The plant, according to a report of the Special Officer appointed by the Government of Bengal, spreads over an area of 4,269 square miles in ten of the badly infected districts of the province of Bengal, and is regarded as a menace to agriculture in general. The eradication of water hyacinth has thus become a problem of very great importance and attempts to destroy it by spraying arsenic and other chemicals have been resorted to from time to time without any practical success. The high potassium chloride content already known, led the Department of Agriculture to establish an experimental station to extract this salt during the War-period. For various reasons, the chief amongst which being the adulteration of the ash with sand and earthly matters, the venture was discontinued and the programme of combating the growth of the weed in this way was abandoned. We were at this time examining the nature of cellulose in different species of wood with a view to their utilisation for the production of power alcohol. Our attention was naturally drawn to the plant, in view specially of its rich potash content, after extraction of which the fibre would be available for saccharification, and subsequent fermentation. Although the technical bearing of this problem would hardly be within the scope of this communication the chemical data accruing from this investigation are considered to be of sufficient interest and are recorded here.

The green plant, on drying in the sun, loses about 95% of its weight and shrinks into a pale yellowish brown straw with dark roots, having a volume approximately one fifteenth of the green substance. Analysis of the green plant shows it to contain 3.7% organic matter and 1.1% ash. Although the green plant in all its

* The samples examined in this paper were collected from the suburbs of Calcutta.

parts shows the presence of starch, the dry plant does not show a trace of it. If, however, the green plant is quickly dried in a steam-oven, the presence of starch is unmistakable. The probable inference, therefore, is that the disappearance of the starch on gradual drying is due to the photochemical decomposition of starch through the intervention of chlorophyll. An analysis of the average root shows 0.07% starch which works out at approximately 1.4% on the air-dried substance. The average content of starch in the leaf and the stem is 0.018% on the green substance or 0.36% on the air-dried. The recognition of the presence of starch is important in studying the bacterial fermentation of the green plant to which detailed reference will be made later.

In course of the experiment the root, the leaf and the stem as also the total weed have been separately investigated, both with regard to the potassium chloride content as also to the alcohol obtainable from them. As is obvious, to ascertain the relative proportion in weight between the different parts of water hyacinth is not very easy, as they differ greatly according to their growth. The average of several determinations may be given as below:

Stem	56.0	per cent.
Leaf	14.0	
Root	30.0	
Total.			100.0	

This, however, by no means, can be accepted as anything more than a very crude approximation. Experiments conducted to determine the percentages of ash and potassium chloride in the different parts of the dried plant gave the following results:—

		Stem.	Leaf.	Root.
Ash	...	24.9%	18.1%	23%
KCl	...	14.2%	5.5%	7.5%

The total plant on ignition leaves an ash, the percentage of which varies between 19.75 and 23 on the air-dried substance. Below is a proximate analysis of the air-dried plant and its ash.

(a) *Analysis of the air dried plant —*

Moisture	13.46 per cent.
Soluble in benzene	1.15
* Soluble in benzene alcohol mixture	7.70
Soluble in cold water	21.64
Soluble in hot water	... 23.64
Soluble in 1 per cent NaOH	45.51
Lignin	.. 11.31
Pentosan	.. 13.33
Cellulose (Cross and Bevan's method)	... 21.89
Cellulose (ClO ₂ method)	42.23
Total nitrogen (Kjeldahl)	... 1.45-1.73
Volatile matter	... 62.4
Total pentosan in cellulose (Cross & Bevan)	. 1.53 gms
Total Pentosan in cellulose (ClO ₂ method)	12.04
Total α cellulose in cellulose (Cross & Bevan)	16.94
Total α cellulose in cellulose (ClO ₂ method).	16.49

The approximate percentage composition of the air dried sample may therefore be represented as below —

Moisture	13.46 per cent.
Ash	... 19.75
Fat & wax	7.70
α, β and γ Cellulose	42.23
Lignin	... 11.31
Nitrogen and its compounds	5.55
Total = 100.00	

Analysis of the Ash —

	Sample I	Sample II
Cl'	... 24.18	25.56
CO ₂ '	4.92	6.46
SO ₄ "	4.68	4.72
P ₂ O ₅	6.06	6.21
SiO ₂	9.32	2.44
Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ O ₃	13.21	13.31
CaO	9.08	9.39
Potassium	26.60	32.00
Sodium	... 2.02	

The high percentage of alumina led us to think that it might be due to any adhering clay. Sample I represents an ordinary sample but

* The extract contained practically no nitrogen. Nitrogen in the residue = 2.23%.

sample II represents a washed and cleaned sample. The difference, however, was only noticed in the silica-content which shows the general richness of the plant in alumina, as the iron is present only in traces in the ash.

The primary importance of the ash cannot be regarded as being wholly due to the large amount of potassium chloride present in it, as, in addition, quite a substantial amount of calcium phosphate and alkali carbonate are present in it (*vide* analysis). Extraction of the ash with water completely removes the chlorides, sulphates and a part of the carbonates giving a residue of calcium phosphate, calcium carbonate, alumina and silica. The percentage of alkali carbonate in the ash varies, according to the source of supply and the mode of incineration, from 1.5 to 9 per cent. If we accept any figure from 3 to 5% as average, the ash would then be comparable in richness to some of the alkali sands in India and Burma and as such, may be of some value. The insoluble calcium phosphate may be rendered available for use as manure, adding thereby to the value of the dried plant.

Acetylation of the dried Water hyacinth.

This was attempted in order to obtain some fresh information as to the condition in which lignin is present in a ligno cellulose, that is to say, whether it exists in chemical combination or in physical adsorption. 10 Gms. of the dried water hyacinth were ground and passed through a seventy mesh sieve; this was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus for 18 hours with a mixture of equal volumes of benzene and absolute alcohol, in order to free it from fat and resin and then heated with 60 gms. of acetic anhydride to boiling under reflux for 15 hours on a sand-bath. The mass was filtered, washed repeatedly with acetic anhydride and finally with chloroform in order to remove any soluble triacetate (of which there was practically very little). The mass was next extracted with boiling ether in a Soxhelt apparatus in order to remove the least trace of acetic acid and acetic anhydride that might have been left. This was then finally dried in vacuum before analysis. A weighed quantity of the product was treated with a definite volume of $N/10$ -caustic soda and allowed to stand 24 hours after which period the excess of alkali was titrated with $N/10$ -sulphuric acid. The amount of alkali which was used up was expressed in term of CH_3CO . Thus, in a typical example, 0.6314 gm. of the acetylated product

required 38.0 c.c. of *N*/10-alkali for saponification, corresponding to 25.89% CH_3CO . A blank on the powder before acetylation corresponded to 5.6% CH_3CO . The acetylation was thus effected upto 21.74%.¹ The acetylated product, however, contained the lignin and ash which can be seen from the following analysis:—

Lignin	12.44 per cent.
Residue after ClO_2 treatment	67.40
Ash	17.28
Pentosan	14.80

The cellulose acetate was separated from the lignin by treatment of the acetylated product with a 2% solution of chlorine peroxide free from hydrochloric acid and chlorine. The acetyl value of the acetate left was 30.27% corresponding to 20.4% CH_3CO on the initial acetylated product. This would seem to indicate that the acetylation, on treatment with acetic anhydride, was restricted mostly to the cellulose part of the ligno-cellulose, the blank acetyl value probably referring in part, at any rate, to lignin and hemi-cellulose. It should also be noted here that in the process of acetylation, the hemi-cellulose part is not removed as the product contained 14.8% pentosan and gave on saccharification with concentrated hydrochloric acid 42.6% reducing sugar. If, on the other hand, the raw material is first deprived of its lignin content by treatment with chlorine peroxide and the total cellulose so obtained acetylated as before, then the acetylated product contains 23.48% CH_3CO and making correction for the blank which was found to contain 3.6% CH_3CO , it becomes only 20.82% CH_3CO and not 30.27%. This difference may be due either to a change in the general constitution of cellulose by the treatment of chlorine peroxide or by the delignification of the original fibre. If the delignification causes a change in the chemical constitution of cellulose, it may not be far wrong to conclude that lignin was probably in chemical combination with the cellulose. On treatment of the acetylation product of the cellulose prepared by the chlorine peroxide method, with 17.5% caustic soda solution in the cold for 30 minutes, 59.3% of its weight is lost, indicating the removal not only of the acetyl group but also of the

¹ 100 grams of the acetylated fibre contain 100—25.89=74.11 grams fibre. Blank on the fibre=5.6% CH_3CO or $74.11 \times 5.6 \times \frac{1}{100} = 4.15$ on 74.11 grams of fibre. Therefore % of fibre acetylated=25.89—4.15=21.74.

hemi-cellulose portion. This latter is obtained on acidification of the alkali extract with acetic acid as a white amorphous powder. It is worthy of notice here that on acetylation of fibre by boiling with acetic anhydride, a cellulose acetate goes into solution which can be precipitated by ether and can be crystallised from chloroform. This corresponds to a triacetate and has the same acetyl value and physical characteristics as those of the one obtained by acetylating either the crude or the chlorine peroxide-cellulose by a mixture of acetic acid and acetic anhydride in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid to the extent of 5% of the weight of the acetylating mixture. The acetyl value of such an acetate was found to be 44.97% (triacetate requires 44.79% CH_3CO). The quantity, however, of the triacetate obtained in the filtrate by the anhydride process is very small. The residue from the acetylation of the chlorine peroxide-cellulose by the cold method, contained 15.8% CH_3CO . The action of chlorine peroxide on the acetylated product, whether from the crude or from the purified cellulose, does not cause any alteration in the acetyl value, although lignin or acetylated lignin is removed by it. It was also found that the acetyl value of the triacetate remained unchanged after treatment with chlorine peroxide. That the hemi-cellulose remains intact after acetylation is proved by the fact that the pentose content practically suffers no diminution. Thus 0.6714 gm. acetylated crude fibre on distillation with hydrochloric acid (d 1.06) and precipitation of the distillate with phloroglucinol, gave 0.1072 gm. phloroglucide corresponding to 14.8% pentosan (calculated pentosan = 14.53%). Further, as mentioned above, treatment of acetylated chlorine peroxide-cellulose with 17.5% caustic soda for 30 minutes, removes the hemi-cellulose and the acetyl groups, leaving α -cellulose behind: 0.8576 gm. acetylated chlorine peroxide-cellulose on treatment with 17.5% caustic soda solution in the cold for half an hour and then on being washed with 8% caustic soda, dilute acetic acid and finally with distilled water till free from acetic acid, gave on drying 0.3496 gm. α -cellulose corresponding to 40.7% α -cellulose. This is equivalent to 22.2% α -cellulose on the dried crude fibre. The α -cellulose on the dried crude fibre was found to be 21.3%. The behavior of the triacetate, that is, the variety which is soluble in chloroform and acetone, is however different. The action of 17.5% alkali removes only the acetyl group leaving the pure α -cellulose behind. It should be noticed in this connection that the chlorine peroxide-cellulose shows

in the blank an acid value of 3.6%. It is reasonable to expect that in the absence of lignin which was dissolved out by the chlorine peroxide solution, this acid value is anchored on to the hemi-cellulose part.

Lignin isolated by Willstätter's method on acetylation with acetic anhydride by boiling for 15 hours on a sand-bath, required caustic soda corresponding to 23.74% CH_3CO . The blank corresponded to 12.56% CH_3CO .²

Saccharification of Water hyacinth.

As the conversion of the cellulosic material into fermentable sugars formed the chief objective of this work, it was conducted under widely different conditions with a view to determine the most suitable one for the technical production of "power alcohol." The air-dried plant was accordingly treated with sulphuric or hydrochloric acids of various strengths at different temperatures (autoclaves being used where necessary). The plant was either treated with the acid after extraction of soluble matter by boiling with water (or 5% solution of sulphuric acid) or the plant was directly treated with the acid after extraction of soluble matters by water digestion under pressure and heat. The general methods followed in the experiments were as follows:—

(1). *Saccharification after extraction with boiling water.*— 10 Gm. of air-dried plant cut into small pieces were repeatedly boiled with water till the filtrate showed the absence of chlorides. The remaining fibre on being dried at 105° weighed about 6.3 gm. The total filtrate was evaporated to dryness and carefully ignited at

² Of the three methods generally adopted for acetylation, we have intentionally followed the anhydride boiling process in this work in order to avoid as far as possible any change taking place in the cellulose or ligno-cellulose complex. Acetylation in the presence of a catalyst, for instance, sulphuric acid, introduces the possibility of some sort of hydrolytic change, and as such cannot be regarded as being free from objections. While in a subsequent communication we hope to throw some more light on the nature of combination between the cellulose and the lignin complex, it may be stated at this stage that the isolation of a triacetate soluble in chloroform takes place only after some change in the cellulose is brought about by the catalyst, and as such, the formation of a diacetate by anhydride boiling whether of the purified cellulose or of the crude ligno-cellulose fibre, can be held as a sort of evidence in favour of the chemical combination of cellulose with lignin in ligno-cellulose. This statement, however, is made with great reservation at this stage.

a low heat in order to avoid volatilisation of potassium chloride. On being titrated with *N*/10-silver nitrate, the following percentages of chlorides calculated as KCl were obtained:—

Expt. No.	...	38	47	50	53	54	55	56	306
KCl (per cent.)		12·00	11·80	10·88	12·22	12·75	10·90	9·68	12·97
									Mean 11·65%.

The residue (63%) still contained about 0·20 to 0·21 per cent. chloride in it and a content of ash varying from 5 to 7% on the weight of the original plant.³ The main filtrate on evaporation to dryness leaves a soft solid which was found to contain 0·408% nitrogen on the original air dried plant corresponding to 2·57% of proteid matter. The residual fibre still contained 0·924% nitrogen. It was also noticed that the residue contained 20·6% pentosan, *i.e.*, 12·98 on the original fibre and hence the extraction of the plant with boiling water practically removed no pentosan.

The residual fibre was next treated with varying quantities of sulphuric acid at various dilutions under different pressures in the autoclave. A few of the results are given in the Table I below.

TABLE I.

Saccharification of air-dried water hyacinth after extraction with boiling water.

Vol. of dil acid to 100 gm. original.	Wt. of H ₂ SO ₄ to 100 gm. original.	Pressure in atmospheres.	Time in minutes.	Per cent. of Reducing sugar on original.	Per cent. of pentose on original.
700 c.c.	2 gm.	6	30	5·0	—
"	4	"	"	9·7	—
"	8	"	"	11·6	9·6
"	4	9	"	9·8	—
200	"	"	"	8·7	—
700	8	"	"	12·8	9·8
"	18	3	60	15·2	—
"	18	"	30	13·2	—

³ *N.B.*—Henceforth all the results will be expressed and the calculations made on the air-dried water hyacinth unless otherwise stated.

It is interesting to note here that in cases where the yield of sugar was very low, the solution on hydrolysis by heating with dilute hydrochloric acid at 80° gave a reducing value corresponding to about 8 to 9% reducing sugar. Estimation of pentose by distilling the solution with 12% hydrochloric acid solution gave from 9 to 10% pentose calculated on the original fibre. The sugar solution was practically unfermentable, only 7 to 10% at the most suffered fermentation by yeast. Osazone prepared from this solution melted at 159-160° and hence it was concluded that the sugar was practically pentose. Hydrolysis of the residue for the second time with varying concentration of acid under different pressures was further studied which, however, gave a very small yield of sugar (3.6%) of which about 50% was fermentable. It was thought advisable, therefore, to deprive the plant of its pentose-yielding constituents and then effect the hydrolysis. Accordingly, experiments were conducted to determine the suitability of pentosan extraction by boiling with an excess of 5% sulphuric acid on the assumption that such a treatment might perhaps convert the cellulosic material into such a condition that further hydrolysis with dilute acids under pressure might give a greater yield of fermentable sugar with minimum quantity of acid

(2) *Saccharification after extraction of the hyacinth with 5% sulphuric acid by boiling.*—100 Gm. air-dried water hyacinth cut into small pieces were boiled with 1500 c.c. of 5% sulphuric acid solution for half an hour. The remaining fibre, on being washed, pressed and dried, weighed on an average 40-42 gm. An estimation of sugar in the filtrate gave about 12-13% reducing sugar and contained on an average 9.4-10.2% chloride calculated as potassium chloride. Most part of the sugar was pentose but occasionally 3 to 4 per cent. hexoses were also present. In this operation 2.5 gm. of sulphuric acid were used up, but the solution could be used over and over again for the extraction of a few fresh lots of water hyacinth. It was found that sulphuric acid of strengths 2-4% required a good length of time to free the plant of its pentosan content. But the volume of the 5% acid solution could be profitably diminished to 500 c.c. if the boiling be continued for at least 4-5 hours with a reflux condenser. Subsequent saccharification was done on the residue thus obtained and a few results calculated on the original air-dried plant are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Saccharification of the residue after boiling air-dried water hyacinth with 5% sulphuric acid.

Vol. of acid on 100 gm. of the original.	Wt. of acid on 100 gm. of the original.	Pressure in atmospheres.	Time in minutes.	Sugar on original.
400 c.c.	2 gm.	10	30	3.96 per cent.
200	6	"	"	2.72
400	"	"	"	3.42
"	8	8	"	2.19
"	"	9	45	3.44
"	"	"	30	3.72

From the above table it is evident that the yield of reducing sugar can hardly be expected to be greater than 4%. As the amount of pentoses present in the sugar solution as determined by the phloroglucinol method rarely exceeded 1.2%, it was believed that most of the sugar was fermentable. This was further corroborated by fermentation experiments which showed that on an average 75.85% of the sugar was fermentable. A second hydrolysis of the residue with 8% sulphuric acid and 200 c.c. of water at 9 atmospheres for 15 minutes gave the best yield of reducing sugar *i.e.* 3.0%, of which about 95% was fermentable.

(3) *Direct saccharification of the air-dried water hyacinth by dilute sulphuric acid.*—In the process of boiling water hyacinth with 5% sulphuric acid as a preparatory treatment for the production of a residue most suitable for the hydrolysis to follow, most of the potassium chloride and the pentose-yielding constituents present in the raw fibre were no doubt removed, and even admitting that the potassium chloride could be recovered, the process required a large excess of sulphuric acid and the yield of sugar was not good. Hence our investigation was carried out directly on the air-dried water hyacinth without any previous treatment. The hyacinth was digested directly with dilute acids under pressure, expecting that this may extract the potassium chloride, the pentosans and perhaps some appreciable quantities of fermentable sugar in addition. A few of the results are given in the following table.

TABLE III.

Saccharification of 100 gm. air-dried water hyacinth with dilute sulphuric acid.

1st Hydrolysis.						2nd Hydrolysis.					
Vol. of dil. acid (c.c.).	Wt. of acid. (gm.).	Press. in atms.	Time in mins.	Sugar %.	Pentose %.	Vol. of dil. acid (c.c.).	Wt. of acid. (gm.).	Press. in atms.	Time in mins.	Sugar %	Fermentation %.
200	0.25	6	15	2.83	...	200	8	8	30	7.15	...
"	"	8	"	3.70	...	300	6	9	"	6.35	...
"	1.0	10	"	4.40	...	400	8	10	"	5.14	...
"	2.0	"	"	7.35
"	"	"	30	8.10
100	"	9	15	7.50	...	400	8	9	30	6.50	...
200	3.0	3	"	4.90	...	80	"	"	"	11.54	55
"	"	"	60	11.70	...	"	"	"	"	9.48	69
"	4.0	"	15	5.10	...	60	6	10	"	8.45	59
700	"	9	30	8.30
200	6.0	8	15	7.00
330	8.0	9	"	10.30	...	330	8	9	15	5.00	...
700	9.0	3	60	14.00	12.57
"	18.0	"	"	15.00	10.09
"	"	"	30	13.75	12.13	700	8	9	30	4.35	...

Though the amount of sugar obtained in the first hydrolysis varied between wide limits under varying conditions of pressure and quantity of acid used, it is to be noted here that the sugar solution on further hydrolysis gave a reducing value corresponding on an average to 5.5% reducing sugar and hence the results are similar to those of the hydrolysis of the residue after extraction with boiling water. All the potassium chloride was practically removed. Only a little fermentable sugar was obtained as was evident from the fact that the hydrolysed solution contained about 10-12% of pentoses. A second hydrolysis gave sugar of which on an average 50-60% was fermentable but no regularity was observed in their yields. The conjecture, therefore, was that the cellulose on heating with dilute acids under pressure becomes somewhat modified in its properties, depending upon the condition to which it is subjected. Since acids as weak as 0.25% can extract the pentosan, it was expected that perhaps a

simple hot water digestion under high pressure may serve the purpose and leave the cellulosic material unmodified as far as the saccharification process is concerned.

(4) *Saccharification of water hyacinth after water digestion under pressure.*—After a large number of experiments, it was found that 100 gm. of air-dried water hyacinth heated with 200 c.c. of water at 9 atmospheres for 15 minutes effected the extraction of potassium chloride as well as 85-90% of the pentosans present in the raw material. The liquid extract was made up to a known volume and an aliquot part carefully evaporated and incinerated gave the following percentages of chlorides calculated as potassium chloride.

Expt.	...	37	43	45	49	53	91	701	109	
KCl.	...	8.55	14.35	9.25	10.3	10.0	12.39	13.58	12.32	14.
Expt.	...	307	312	372	116	121	124	140	141	
KCl.	...	12.72	11.92	12.99	16	13.36	10.77	14.35	13.48	
						Mean.			12.15%	

The analysis of a sample of potassium chloride derived from the plant is given below:—

Qualitative:—Na, K, Mg. (trace), SO''_4 , Cl', CO''_3 , $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})'''_6$ (trace) CNS' (trace), NO'_2 (trace).

Quantitative:—

Cl'	45.10 per cent.
SO''_4	2.70
CO''_3	0.60
Potassium	49.90
Sodium	1.60
Mg, $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})'''_6$, CNS, etc.	0.10
			Total	100.00

The potassium chloride so obtained is therefore 95.3% pure and is of a high grade of purity. If instead of using 2 parts of water for every one part of the raw material, less quantity of water were used, the mass became charred thereby causing damage to the cellulosic material.

The residue from the pressure-water digestion was subjected to hydrolysis as usual under different conditions. A few of the typical results are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.
Saccharification of 100 gm. air-dried water hyacinth after pressure water-digestion.
 1st hydrolysis. 2nd hydrolysis.

Vol. of dil. acid (c.c.).	Wt. of acid (gm.).	Press in atmos.	Time in mins.	Sugar %	Fermentation %.	Vol. of dil. acid (c.c.).	Wt. of acid (gm.).	Press in atmos.	Time in mins.	Sugar %	Fermentation %.
250	1.0	9	30	3.17	...	250	1.0	9	30	0.57	...
"	2.0	"	"	4.08	...	"	2.0	"	"	3.80	...
500	2.5	"	"	5.49	...	"	2.5	"	"	2.75	...
210	"	"	"	8.20	...	120	5.0	"	"	4.50	...
500	3.0	"	"	6.90	...	500	3.0	"	"	2.81	...
250	4.0	6	"	8.3	62	"	4.0	6	"	1.80	...
200	4.5	9	15	8.5	40	100	2.25	9	15	4.5	...
"	5.0	"	"	8.2	...	"	"	"	"	3.4	...
210	"	"	"	8.97	42	210	5.0	"	"	4.3	80
230	"	"	"	8.85	46	100	2.5	"	"	1.81	...
"	"	"	"	"	"	120	"	"	"	1.90	...
"	"	"	"	"	"	"	50	"	"	3.10	...
240	"	"	"	8.21	...	100	2.5	"	"	3.40	...
250	"	"	"	6.40
500	"	"	"	6.40
1000	"	"	4.5	7.8	65.3	250	8.0	8	30	3.07	...
"	"	"	"	"	"	500	5.0	"	45	2.60	...
"	"	"	"	"	"	1000	"	"	"	2.53	...

TABLE IV (continued).

1st hydrolysis.					2nd hydrolysis.						
Vol. of dil. acid (c.c.)	Wt. of acid (gm.)	Press. in atmos.	Time in mins.	Sugar %	Fermentation %	Vol. of dil. acid (c.c.)	Wt. of acid (gm.)	Press. in atmos.	Time in mins.	Sugar %	Fermentation %
80	6.0	9	30	4.42	...	80	0	9	30	7.13	95
80	"	"	"	5.90
160	"	"	"	7.70
200	"	"	15	7.84	...	300	6.0	8	30	3.9	...
"	"	"	"	"	...	60	"	"	"	7.13	85
250	"	"	"	9.64	...	250	"	"	15	5.30	83
80	8.0	9	"	7.50	72						
160	"	"	"	8.40	80						
200	"	"	30	7.80	...						
"	"	"	5	2.96	...						
800	"	"	80	7.60	35	400	5.8	8	30	8.17	...
330	"	"	15	9.60	67	330	"	"	15	4.93	78
"	"	"	"	"	"	120	3.0	"	"	2.90	81
400	"	"	30	8.50	45	400	2.0	0	30	1.30	...
"	9.0	"	"	8.70	...						
250	10.0	8	5	2.65	...						
1000	"	"	30	8.75	...						
700	18.0	3	60	16.00	18	4	2.0	9	80	3.9	...

From an analysis of the tables above, it would appear that a semi-normal solution of sulphuric acid under a pressure of 9 atmospheres causes the best saccharification, and that in the second acid hydrolysis, the reducing sugar is practically completely fermentable, indicating the presence of small quantities of pentose only. From a consideration of the technical feasibility of the process it has been found that a fairly good yield of fermentable sugar is obtained by using on the air-dried water hyacinth 4.5% sulphuric acid for the first hydrolysis and 2.25% sulphuric acid for the second.

The residue left after the pressure-water digestion of 100 gm. air-dried water hyacinth is about 62 gm. and contains 0.789 gm. nitrogen, 0.901 gm. of nitrogen having passed into the extract. The residue after the first hydrolysis with 4.5% acid at 9 atmospheres weighs about 42 gm. and on further hydrolysis with 2.25 gm. acid at 9 atmospheres, weighs about 25 gm. and has a calorific value of 7700 B.Th.U. Its appearance is brownish black and is quite suitable as fuel, specially under a somewhat forced draught. The final residue still retains 0.32% nitrogen.

(5) *Saccharification with concentrated hydrochloric acid.*

Experiments were also conducted to study the amount of reducing sugar obtainable by saturation of the hyacinth by hydrochloric acid gas at different temperatures. The material was taken in a round bottom flask moistened with three times its weight of water and hydrochloric acid gas passed through the mass, which was kept at a definite temperature by providing cooling arrangements till no further absorption took place. The flask was tightly corked and allowed to stand for an hour at the room temperature, at the end of which the acid was removed by a suction pump. When the major portion of hydrochloric acid was removed which was evident from the disappearance of frothing, the temperature was gradually raised to 70° on a water-bath. The suction was continued till the mass became nearly dry when sufficient quantity of water was added so that the acidity of the solution was reduced to about 1%. This required water about 10 times the weight of the hyacinth taken. This was boiled for an hour, filtered and washed. The filtrate was neutralised with chalk and again filtered. The sugar content of the solution was estimated and then it was subjected to fermentation. The amount of fermentable sugar was estimated by direct titration as also from a determination of the specific gravity of the distillate obtained by the fractional distillation of

the fermented liquor. The mean of several experiments are given in the Table V. It will be found that the maximum yield of sugar on an average is 34.12%. In some of the experiments reducing value as high as 39.2% was obtained corresponding to 95% of the theoretical yield on cellulose and hemi-cellulose combined. During the course of the experiments, preliminary trials were made to study the significance of the process of boiling after the hydrochloric acid had been removed by suction. It was found that before boiling, about 40% of the totally available sugar was already present in the filtrate. It is thus probable that an ester of hydrochloric acid is first formed with the cellulose which gradually breaks down into simple reducing sugars even at ordinary temperatures but more so, at higher temperatures. Further experiments in this direction are in progress. The table also shows that the concentration of hydrochloric acid plays an important part in the process of saccharification and that fermentation by yeast is not inhibited by the presence of chlorides in the solution to an extent hitherto believed.

TABLE V.

Saccharification by concentrated hydrochloric acid.

(a) 100 gms. air-dried water hyacinth was taken.

Expt.	Temp.	Sugar.	Fermentation.
394	0°	34.12 per cent.	60 per cent.
186	10°	31.80	51
285	20°	26.64	44
279	30°	24.06	38

(b) Residue from 100 gms. air-dried water hyacinth after pressure-water digestion.

...	0°	26.30	80
...	10°	22.68	75
...	20°	19.80	71
...	30°	15.70	66

(c) Residue from 100 gms. air-dried water hyacinth left after successive digestion with water and 5% sulphuric acid at 9 atoms.

127	0°	12.6	90.0
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(d) Residue from 100 gms. air-dried water hyacinth left after successive digestion under 9 atmospheric pressures with water, 5% sulphuric acid and 2.5% sulphuric acid.

Expt.	Temp.	Sugar.	Fermentation.
197	0°	7.47	95.0

Saccharification of cellulose.—Saccharification of different kinds of celluloses prepared from water hyacinth was also studied with 5% sulphuric acid and 10 times water at 9 atmospheres for 15 minutes. The following results were obtained:—

Nature of cellulose.	Sugar.	Contribution of sugar from 100 gms. hyacinth.
Cellulose (Cross and Bevan) ...	19.53 per cent.	4.07
α -Cellulose from Do ..	19.16	3.26
Cellulose (chlorine peroxide) ...	25.80	10.84
α -Cellulose from Do ...	20.70	3.41

It is evident from the above table that the α -cellulose becomes modified, if at all, to the same extent by the chlorine or chlorine peroxide treatment. The cellulose prepared by ClO_2 method was also digested with water at 9 atmospheres for 15 minutes; on estimation of sugar in the filtrate, it was found to yield 5.22% sugar. The sugar solution on hydrolysis corresponded to an yield of 11.72% reducing sugars. The presence of hemi-cellulose in chlorine peroxide cellulose is thus proved.

Bacterial decomposition of the plant.

The large quantity of hemi-cellulose present in the plant suggested the possibility of easier disintegration of the hyacinth fibre by the action of bacteria. We understand similar work is being carried out by Dr. G. J. Fowler in the Sir Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Cawnpore. As our preliminary results appear sufficiently encouraging, a short summary of the work is given below. In all our experiments we used septic tank fluids and the green plant in preference to the dried one as the latter did not decompose as readily as the former. The fermentation which commenced within a day or two after the addition of the tank-liquor continued over several days till a p_H value of 3.8 was reached. At this stage the concentration of potassium chloride was 0.2% and that of acid 0.0727% in term of acetic acid. The temperature employed was 38°-40°. A typical experiment

yielded 1800 c.c. of gas in course of seven days from 100 gm. green water hyacinth having the following compositions:—

	I	II	III	IV
CO ₂ ...	22.1	21.6	21.4	21.3
O ₂ ..	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.5
CH ₄ ..	51.6	52.7	52.8	52.7
H ₂ ..	25.4	25.0	24.6	24.5

The residual pulp from the above experiment was treated with chlorine peroxide solution, in order to estimate the quantity of α , β - and γ -celluloses remaining after fermentation.

100 Gm. green water hyacinth contained 2.1500 gms. total cellulose.

After fermentation and chlorine peroxide treatment, total cellulose is equal to 1.3760 gm. (containing 0.8430 gm., α -cellulose. Therefore the total cellulose fermented is equal to 0.7740 gm. of which 0.533 gm. was hemi-cellulose and 0.241 gm. α -cellulose. This corresponds to a fermentation of 36% of the total cellulose. The volume of gas is however not commensurate with these figures even after allowing for a control experiment and the probable contribution of starch. Further experiments with thermophilic bacteria are in progress.

Destructive distillation of the air-dried plant.

Distillation of 10 gm. of air-dried water hyacinth at 1000° gave about 4.8 litres of gas and a residue of 18% charcoal. The distillation at 500° left 40% charcoal. The composition of the gas is given below:—

	At 1000°.	At 500°
Carbon dioxide ...	8.31	36.90
Unsaturated hydrocarbon ...	Trace.	3.75
Marsh gas ...	11.53	10.94
Carbon monoxide ...	25.74	14.06
Hydrogen ..	33.30	24.5
Oxygen ...	2.57	3.12
Nitrogen ...	18.56	6.75

It would be interesting to conduct experiments to see how far the Mond-gasification of this plant may have any technical importance.¹

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¹ Dr. R. L. Dutt, Industrial Chemist to the Government of Bengal, first drew our attention to Mond-gasification of the plant.